

The Translation Study of Chinese and American Pharmaceutical Profiles from the Perspective of Recontextualization – Regarding GPHL and Merck

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Abstract

Pharmaceutical companies play an important role in defending us against the pandemic. As Chinese pharmaceutical companies enter overseas markets, making contributions to the world, their company profiles need to be adapted to different contexts, such as the American context. Under this circumstance, company profiles with different contexts can provide insight into the discursive relationship between text and context in the study of website translation. In view of this, this study firstly contrasts the English profile of Chinese company Guangzhou Pharmaceutical Holdings Limited (GPHL) with that of American company Merck by genre analysis, then studies the application of (Wodak & Fairclough, 2010)'s "recontextualization" concept to the translation of the company profile—finally, generalizing the translation strategies and recontextualizing mechanism that is suitable for Chinese pharmaceutical companies. It is hoped that this study can deepen the application of recontextualization and thereby give some advice to those Chinese pharmaceutical companies in translating pharmaceutical company profiles.

Keywords: recontextualization, company profile, pharmaceutical companies, translation, genre analysis

1. Introduction

To improve the competitiveness of Chinese pharmaceutical companies in the foreign market, especially during the pandemic, the external communication of corporate culture is particularly critical, and language is an important carrier for intercultural communication. Under this circumstance, many Chinese enterprises, including long-established enterprises, have set up English versions for their corporate profiles. As part of the corporate website, they are the window for corporate outreach, which involves more than retranslation (Wu & Li, 2017). Elements are the linguistic features or resources that company profiles have. Wodak & Fairclough (2010) suggested that elements include explanations, evaluations, and legitimations that can be added to the new context. When elements are translated from one language to another, it's necessary to free them from the original context and accept the new context. The disintegration and recombination of the context are known as recontextualization. Recontextualization has been used for website translation studies over the past few years (Lin, 2021; Zhang & Zhao, 2020; Wu & Li, 2017), but not many have focused on pharmaceutical companies' profile translation. Moreover, those articles tend to pay more attention to the content than structure.

Therefore, this paper aims to apply the recontextualization to the translation study of the Chinese pharmaceutical company profile compared with the American pharmaceutical company profile and combine the genre analysis to find the differences between Chinese pharmaceutical company (GPHL) and American pharmaceutical company (Merck) in constructing corporate profiles and then point out the translating issues about the profile of GPHL. From recontextualization, translation strategies and mechanisms can be explored for the Chinese pharmaceutical companies to improve the translating quality of company profiles. Theoretically, this paper partially fills the gap in profile translation study by combining genre analysis and recontextualization. Practically, it is expected that this study can give some suggestions for the translation of pharmaceutical company profiles from Chinese to English.

2. Literature Review

Context is vital for intercultural communication studies. Recontextualization requires communicators to extract elements and information from the source context and reconstruct them in the new context for communicative purposes (Fairclough, 2010). For translation studies, recontextualization is defined as selecting important information from the source language and reorganizing and rewriting them in the context of the targeted language.

2.1 Recontextualization

Recontextualization is a notion first put forward by Bernstein in his research on pedagogy. It regulates the transformation of discourse within discourse production into the field of its reproduction. It's a process in which texts, signs, or meanings are selected from one social practice and introduced into another (Wu et al., 2016). Linell (1998) believed that recontextualization is a dynamic process, and it means the transfer-transformation of elements from one context to another. He classified it into three parts-intratextual, intertextual, and interdiscursive recontextualization. Recontextualization is not just confined to pedagogy. Fairclough (2003) expanded this concept into discourse and social practices. He believed that recontextualization is the representation of social events and the perspectivation of discourse. A particular type of social event can be represented through different genres and networks of social practices. Meanwhile, communicators' cognition and notions can impact and transform discourse. The relationship between language and social practice is mediated through recontextualization (Altahmazi, 2020). Besides, recontextualization functions as assigning values to tokens in a particular context adapted to the constraints and requirements of a different context, thus re-evaluating and assigning a different value (Fetzer, 2017).

Recontextualization is widely and deeply discussed in many fields, such as social reform and media. Wodak & Fairclough (2010) studied the higher education policies of the European Union and found that the same policy could have different understandings in the various political, cultural, and historical contexts. They brought recontextualization into discourse analysis and explained the disciplinary relationship between this notion and social reform. Wu (2016) applied recontextualization and transformation to the media discourse based on the First-Instance Judgment of the Peng Yu Case. This article explains why a text is interpreted differently in different contexts-media context, judgment context, and reader interpretation context by creating the theoretical framework of the discourse-historical-contextual approach. Media discourse is also analyzed in other methods. Anbin (2021) delineated constructive journalism's conceptual common ground from comparative journalism and intercultural communication. By comparing public opinion surveillance (POS) between western and Chinese journalism, he discovered that POS had been recontextualized as both Western and Chinese journalism has the same goal of serving the people. Still, they hold various news concepts and media eco-system. Still, his research lays the theoretical foundation for recontextualizing constructive journalism in the Chinese social and cultural context.

2.2 *Recontextualization and translation*

Recontextualization is also developed in the study of translation. Moreover, many researchers utilize recontextualization in the translation study of corporate publicity. Wodak (1999) argued that recontextualizing a text or discourse would bring the transformation of meanings through which the new context reflects elements being endowed with different dynamic contextual meanings. Based on the previous categorization and transformation views (Fairclough, 2003; Wodak, 1999), Wu (2016) proposed the following categorization of transformations in the recontextualization process: addition, deletion, abstraction, and rearrangement to analyze the media discourse, which paves the way for his analysis of website translation. Wu & Li (2017) further took website translations of Fortune Global 500 companies as examples to reveal the application of recontextualization and transformation in terms of the categorization of transformations: addition, deletion, rearrangement, and replacement, which enlightens more researchers to use this categorization and has the referential value for the study of website translation strategies. They also believed that the study of website translation should be from the perspective of publicity translation. Other than comparing Chinese company websites with American companies', Zhang & Zhao (2020) utilized the Chinese and English company profiles of the world's top 500 Chinese companies and explored the application of recontextualization, which is beneficial to the external publicity translation of Chinese companies. Wu & Dong (2020) concentrated on the transmission of Chinese culture. They elicited the website translation of Confucius Institute and concluded the new principles of recontextualization for this type of website translation: dynamic state, detailed demonstration, immediate feedback, and complete message. Altahmazi (2020) showed the multimodal and cross-lingual recontextualization in the online news site. He found that recontextualization existed in a different ideological narrative. Wang (2021) shed light on the website translation of China General Nuclear Power Corporation and the translation issues of the typical Chinese state company. She also pointed out the importance of recontextualization in corporate culture transmission and in entering foreign markets.

According to the literature review, it can be concluded that many scholars are beginning to putting recontextualization into the study of website translation, especially company profile translation. Still, a few of them notice the website translation of pharmaceutical companies, though they make significant contributions to preventing the pandemic, and their publicity translations closely connect with overseas business. On top of that, previous literature did not set clear boundaries between structure and content dimension under recontextualization. Therefore, it's expected that studying the translation of pharmaceutical companies can help Chinese pharmaceutical companies enter the foreign markets and benefit people with made-in-China medicines.

3. Method

This paper selects two typical English company profiles from a Chinese pharmaceutical company-GPHL and an American company Merck for a case analysis to partially fill the gap. It integrates two approaches: genre analysis and recontextualization for the structural and content dimensions. Genre analysis contrasts the linguistic moves between GPHL and Merck in the structural dimension. Through this approach, structural differences can be found. Based on the linguistic moves, content differences can be further examined by categorizing transformations in the recontextualization (Wu et al., 2016; Wu & Li, 2017). Recontextualization takes place within the same field, the pharmaceutical industry, and within the same genre, company profiles. It's aimed to improve the profile translation of GPHL by those two approaches.

3.1 Genre analysis

Traditionally, the genre is classified into literature and rhetoric. However, following a deeper understanding of discourse analysis, linguists broaden the concept of genre, and they suggest that genre involves all the linguistic events of social practices and communication activities. In general, there are two schools of genre analysis. Australian school is stand by Martin. The Swalesian school, represented by Swale and Bhatia, takes linguistic moves and steps analysis as the starting point for the discourse analysis. Linguistic moves are defined as “a discoursal or rhetorical unit that performs a coherent communicative function in a written or spoken discourse (Swales, 2004). A move can be realized by one clause, one or more sentences, a paragraph, or longer (Cotos et al., 2017). Move analysis is mainly used to study academic articles. Tseng (2018) studied research articles in nine linguistic journals and found three moves: providing a theoretical background, establishing a theoretical framework, and sharpening the significance of one's study. Bhatia (1993) displayed seven moves of promotional letters in the business field, including establishing credentials, introducing the offer, offering incentives, enclosing documents, soliciting a response, using pressure tactics, and ending politely. He also believed that communicative purposes need to be figured out before analyzing the linguistic moves. In our paper, the move is seen as a stretch of linguistic resources that serve the particular communicative purposes of publicity. Translation strategies can be realized through move analysis.

Many investigators have been concerned about business documents employing genre analysis in recent years. For example, Liu (2012) conducted the quantitative and qualitative approaches to study Chinese and American pharmaceutical companies' profiles. She found that realization is quite different, although they have similar linguistic moves. Deng (2013) started with the angle of intercultural communication under genre analysis. It is found that Chinese and English company profiles own different linguistic moves, and they have their unique linguistic features. Li & Zhu (2020) researched CEO statements in English from Chinese and western annual reports. Through the corpus linguistic approach and move-step analysis, they discovered that although both of them have the same communicative purposes, the realizations of linguistic moves are quite different. The linguistic moves of western annual reports are more flexible than those of Chinese annual reports. From the literature review, it can be found that genre analysis has been widely used in business documents and contrastive analysis. However, not many combine genre analysis and recontextualization with studying the business documents, not to mention the website translation. Moreover, this paper attempts to explain why translate in this way concerning the translation of corporate publicity materials.

3.2 Move analysis

GPHL is a traditional Chinese pharmaceutical company that works on Chinese patent medicine, herbal medicine, chemical-pharmaceutical raw material, healthcare products, etc. This company plays a part in the transmission of traditional Chinese medicine culture, and it owns the overseas business. Merck is an American pharmaceutical company and ranks one of the Global 500. Its business mainly covers western medicine for treating COVID-19, cardio-metabolic disorders, animal health, etc. On the one hand, they have similar points, such as the rank on the Global 500 and the same industry. On the other hand, differences cannot be ignored either. They have various cultural and social backgrounds, lines of business, and enterprise property. If GPHL wants to accommodate the western market. In that case, it requires modifying its profile translation referring to that of Merck so that western customers can better understand Chinese medicine and Chinese pharmaceutical companies.

As-mentioned previously, communicative purposes need to be given priority and can be concluded as follows: attract the potential customers; show the features and advantages; establish the initial relationship with stakeholders. For the pharmaceutical companies, due to their strong specialty, high-quality company profiles enable stakeholders to understand the lines of business as well. Linguistic moves can be summarized based on the analysis of communicative purposes. Besides, move structure is a configuration of stretches of all the constituent moves of a text that accomplish coherent communicative goals and development ideas (Tseng, 2018). It can be seen that Figure 1 is the structural description of moves of GPHL, and Figure 2 is the move structure of Merck.

Table 1. Move structure of GPHL

Move	Structural description	Percentage of the total number
M1	General introduction	14.15%
S1	Nature	
S2	Product and service	
S3	Capability	
S4	Achievement	
M2	The work of party building	19.51%
M3	Social responsibility	15.83%
M4	Achievement and Capability	44.83%
S1	Subsidiaries	
S2	Intangible cultural heritages	
S3	Trademarks	
S4	Patents	
M5	Development target	5.68%

Table 2. Move structure of Merck

Move	Structural description	Percentage of the total number
M1	General introduction	13.31%
S1	History	
S2	Product and service	
M2	Achievement	1.99%
M3	Mission statement	3.11%
M4	Leadership	3.61%
M5	Capability	2.61%
S1	Employees	
S2	Research and development	
S3	Social responsibility	
M6	Corporate culture and value	36.69%
M7	History	4.48%
M8	Product and service	27.74%
M9	Partner	3.73%
M10	Policies	2.73%

From Figures 1 and 2, it can be seen that the move structure of GPHL and Merck is different as a whole. It can be further discussed based on similarities and differences in move structure. The same move structure is a general introduction, accounting for 14.15% and 13.31%, respectively. Concerning the differences, the work of party building takes up a more significant proportion of the move structure of GPHL, while Merck's company profile does not. Corporate culture and value are the move structure that GPHL's company profile does not possess. Apart from that, the move structure of achievement and capability occupies the most significant proportion of 44.83% for GPHL. At the same time, Merck talks about corporate culture and value altogether with product and service, which accounts for 36.69% and 27.74%.

3.3 Translation strategies

According to transformations of recontextualization, there are four translation strategies: addition, deletion, rearrangement, and abstraction (Wu et al., 2016). However, Wu & Dong (2020) brought another concept of substitution for their study of website translation. As required, there are five translation strategies suitable for the case analysis: addition, substitution, rearrangement, abstraction, and deletion. The move analysis impacts the process of addition, deletion, and rearrangement. Profile translation of GPHL can be improved according to the company profile of Merck through this process. The five translation strategies are explained as follows:

3.3.1 Addition

Fairclough (2003) suggested that elements such as explanations, evaluations, and legitimations may be added according to the new context. When it comes to the profile translation, additions complement some illustrations of characteristics and historical or cultural background. It also implies adding some statistics or figures. Adding the move structure and explaining medical terms are significant for the two specific cases. As linguistic moves have been compared, it can be found that

information about corporate culture and value can be added. Leadership can also be complemented if necessary.

Aside from that, GPHL mentions its goal of development as follows:

GPHL develop its core business Grand Southern TCM, Grand Health, Grand Commerce, and Grand Medical Treatment.

Source link: www.gpc.com.cn/

Its profile translation contains medical strategies characterized by vogue meaning. Western customers would like to receive more objective and specific information. Therefore, they would like to know more about the particular content of Grand Southern TCM, Grand Health, Grand Commerce, and Grand Medical Treatment.

The added information should cater to the benefits of western customers as well. For example, Merck writes its strategies and policies with functions:

We support public policies that advance the interests of patients, improve public health and promote access to medicines and innovation. (Source link: www.msd.at/en/msd-worldwide)

The principle of “Customer first” needs profiles to be attractive. They should know what customers want to know, such as the functions of products and services. On the contrary, when it comes to the introduction of products and services, GPHL states as follows:

It also boasts six state-level intangible cultural heritages: Xingqun Xiasangju Granules, BYS Dashen Kouyangqing Granules, Wanglaoji herbal Tea, and Chenliji traditional Chinese medical culture, Pangaoshou traditional medical culture, and the preparation process of Zhongyi Baoying Compound. (Source link: www.gpc.com.cn/)

The names of Chinese-type medicine are endowed with Chinese characteristics. From this paragraph, transliteration is adopted to translate medical terms. This translation strategy is not concerned with cultural differences and readability. It's suggested that add the efficiency and ingredients of medicines so that western customers can learn more about Chinese medicine and Chinese medicine culture. For instance, when talking about moving the structure of products and services, Merck introduces them as listed:

Cardio-metabolic disorders

We are determined to find solutions for the most serious chronic health challenges, such as cardiovascular disease and diabetes. (Source link: www.msd.at/en/msd-worldwide)

Cardio-metabolic disorders are also the medical term and can make reading difficult. But it explains “the most serious chronic health challenges” with the sentence. Customers can guess that this term is related to chronic diseases. That's why GPHL can correlate its medical terms with its efficiency.

3.3.2 Substitution

Wu & Dong (2020) regarded replacement as replacing the representation of a social event with another social event. The premise is that both of them hold similar features. For the profile translation, substitution was more likely to be realized by referential strategy, in which the name of the company should be replaced by the personal pronoun “we.” GPHL prefers to use its company name to show its authority, which widens the distance between the company and western customers, while Merck would instead use “we” to narrow down the space. The following two examples belong to the same move of general introduction.

GPHL is a well-established enterprise with over 400 years of history. (Source link: www.gpc.com.cn)

And Merck states as follows:

For 130 years, we've focused on the next quarter and the next century. (Source link: www.msd.at/en/msd-worldwide)

3.3.3 Deletion

Wodak (2001) argues that when writers represent a social event, they have to choose what to reserve and what to delete. Back to the profile translation of GPHL, it can be seen that there are many phrases with Chinese characteristics, especially the move structure of the work of party building. This move does not exist in the source of Merck. Moreover, GPHL repeatedly tells its patriot spirits as its company spirits. Still, western customers cannot connect patriot spirits with a pharmaceutical company because we do not share the same historical and political background. For instance, when it comes to the linguistic moves of historical knowledge, it talks below:

It has produced a galaxy of revolutionaries, such as Yang Yi, a leader of CPC in early days, advocate and organizer of

Guangzhou Uprising and member of the Standing Committee of the Political Bureau of the CPC Central Committee (Source link: www.gpc.com.cn)

When it talks about the move structure of party building, it states some proper nouns related to Chinese histories, such as “Guangzhou Uprising” “CPC Central Committee” “Yang Yi”, which is difficult for westerners to understand and is not suitable for the communicative purpose. Hence, it’s better to delete the information or represent information in the form of a video so that readers can choose whether to read it or not.

Another piece of information that needed to be deleted in the move structure of the party building is praise and achievement with Chinese characteristics. GPHL demonstrates that:

The CPC Committee of Guangzhou Wanglaoji Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd. has been listed as the “Excellent Grass-root Party Branch of Guangzhou”. (Source link: www.gpc.com.cn)

Because westerners do not recognize those achievements and value the facts, such as statistics and figures, it would be better not to show this type of achievement. All in all, the move structure of party building should be deleted following the cultural differences.

3.3.4 Rearrangement

Rearrangement refers to the change of orders when representing a social event (Fairclough, 2003). According to the analysis of the move, it can be concluded that GPHL writes its achievement in different steps and occupies a more significant proportion than that of Merck. Therefore, it’s helpful to list figures, statistics, and other factual information together, just as Merck does in its move structure of achievement to make the company profile concise and conspicuous. Below is the achievement on Merck’s website.

Our company by the numbers

74k employees

\$13.6 B Research and development investment in 2020

\$3.1 B Total philanthropy in 2019

(Source link: www.msd.at/en/msd-worldwide)

Figures and statistics can deepen the company’s impression, which favors cooperation and investment. On the contrary, GPHL proposes its information about figures and statistics in the move structure of achievement below:

It possesses ten well-known Chinese trademarks, namely GPHL, Baiyunshan, Wanglaoji, Chenliji, Zhongyi, Kangzhiba, Pangaoshou, Tianxin, Hejigong, and Qixing. The brand value of Wanglaoji reaches 108 billion RMB, the No.1 beverage brand in China. In comparison, the brand value of Baiyunshan is estimated to be 28.3 billion RMB, ranking the first among medical brands in China.

“Ten,” “108 billion RMB,” and “28.3 billion RMB” are the statistics that need to be shown in the apparent position to present the company’s capability and convince benefit communities.

Rearrangement can also be used in the move structure of social responsibility of GPHL. Here are two examples:

In Meizhou, GPHL also constructed Wanglaoji’s first ingredient extraction center and the Caizhilin Chinese medicine industrialization service center, creating at least 800 jobs for local people and helping boost the local economy.

The Wanglaoji Charity Fund of RMB 182.8 million set up by Wanglaoji Health has taken an industry-leading stance, donating money and supplies to bring relief to disaster-stricken areas such as Ya’an, Lydian, Wenchuan, Yushu, and Yiliang, and preventing and controlling H7N9, bird flu, and another disease. Total donations have exceeded 1 billion RMB.

(Source link: www.gpc.com.cn)

“800 jobs”, “182.8 million”, and “1 billion” are factual information that needs to be rearranged following the form of Merck. Besides, Merck has the move structure of product and service, which customers are concerned about, while GPHL does not have this structure and talks about it in the move structure of achievement. It is suggested that the part of the product and service should be rearranged and listed as one move other than one step.

3.3.5 Abstraction

Fairclough (2003) indicated that abstraction is the degree of generalization. Wu (2016) thought writers could report a social event specifically or straightforwardly. This notion is suitable for the profile translation as well. Merck begins with a

conclusion before introducing structural descriptions in detail, while GPHL does not abstract its descriptions. The moving structure of products and services is an excellent example of Merck:

We focus on scientific innovation to deliver medicines and vaccines that may help millions of people around the world.
(Source link: www.msd.at/en/msd-worldwide)

This conclusion implies two meanings. Firstly, the scope of business is “medicines and vaccines.” Then, the benefits brought to customers are “help millions of people around the world.” Here is another example of Merck:

Oncology

Our mission is to deliver innovations that extend and improve the lives of people with cancer

Vaccines

Vaccines are one of the greatest public health success stones-and we’ve been discovering, developing, and delivering vaccines to help prevent disease for over 100 years

(Source link: www.msd.at/en/msd-worldwide)

Inversely, GPHL introduces its product and service without a conclusion:

GPHL is dedicated to researching and developing Chinese patent medicine, Chinese herbal medicine, chemical-pharmaceutical raw materials and preparations, biological medicine and healthcare products, and pharmaceutical logistics and distribution and healthcare service.

(Source link: www.gpc.com.cn)

GPHL uses the parallel to show its products and service but lacks a conclusion. “Chinese patent medicine” and “Chinese herbal medicine” are all Chinese medicine, so that they can be categorized into Chinese medicine. The scope of business can be summarized as working on the research and development of Chinese medicine, and those medicines can benefit customers.

Recontextualization has been discussed based on structure and content dimension. Therefore, the recontextualizing principle of company profile translation can be further analyzed at the macro and cognitive levels.

4.1 Recontextualizing principle of company profile translation

As Wu & Dong (2020) put forward the recontextualizing framework of website translation for company cultural transmission, the direction of company profile translation can be concluded based on this and the case study of GPHL and Merck. Our framework explores how to revise the pharmaceutical company profile translation and then figure out the recontextualization process and mechanism to realize companies' publicity from the macro, micro, and cognitive dimensions. This mechanism is conducive to understanding the application of recontextualization in the translation study of company profiles. It may be applicable in other types of website translation. The pattern is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Recontextualization process of company profile translation

In the macro dimension, corporate and language culture have a combined effect on cultural context and the process of de-contextualization due to cultural differences. At the micro-level, genre analysis and recontextualization can be carried out to recontextualize the text concerning the effects of language and culture. Finally, recontextualizing translation should coincide with the cognition and arouse readers' attention; external publicity can be realized through the whole process.

4.2 Translation of corporate publicity

The translated text of GPHL is not applicable to two principles of the Three Principles of "Closeness" (Huang, 2004): closeness to westerners' needs for information about China and proximity to their thinking and language habits. Translation of corporate publicity is regarded as publicity for foreign customers. It functions by letting them know about the company efficiently and directly, promoting commodities and company image, making them accept and buy products, services, and notions, and receiving interests.

However, by comparing the English profile between GPHL and Merck, it can be seen that the structure and content of GPHL do not meet the expectations of foreign customers, and their cultural differences and information needs are underestimated. That means the cognitive level has not finished, so the external publicity cannot be realized. Furthermore, the whole text lacks focus, so the publicity goals are not achieved.

4.3 High and low context

Culture works as the mental strategy for human beings and functions as forming their way of thinking, feeling, and acting (Hofstede, 2001). There are several cultural factors influencing how people see the world. Different patterns of English translations between GPHL and Merck reflect the differences in context. Hall (1976) came up with high and low context, mainly used in intercultural communication. The characteristic of high context is that much information is coded faintly rather than distinctly because people are more dependent on context. It can be explained that the focal points of profile translation of GPHL are not prominent. In contrast, low context is featured by the low amount of information and is not rely so much on

context. The meaning of information can be expressed clearly, so there is no need to guess based on context. To summarize, when the Chinese pharmaceutical company, which is in a high-context country, enters a low-context country, it has to change its information from implicit to explicit.

5. Conclusion

This paper first adopts genre analysis and recontextualization to compare the English company profile between the Chinese pharmaceutical company GPHL and the American company Merck. Through this process, translation issues and strategies can be discovered for GPHL. The research identifies the following five strategies serving publicity and cross-cultural communication were identified: addition, deletion, rearrangement, substitution, and abstraction. And then, it explores the recontextualization mechanism in the external promotion and cross-cultural communication and digs out the reasons for differences in cultural contexts and the Three Principles of Closeness. It is suggested that this paper can provide a new perspective for company profile translation and help construct a discourse system for Chinese pharmaceutical companies. However, limitations should not be ignored either. Firstly, the data is limited, and future studies can select more pharmaceutical company profiles or among a large group of companies from different industries, countries, or cultures. Secondly, statistical analysis and corpus analysis can be applied to increase the objectivity and preciseness of the results.

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References

- Altaf, T. H. M. (2020). Creating realities across languages and modalities: Multimodal recontextualization in the translation of online news reports. *Discourse, Context & Media*, 35, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dcm.2020.100390>
- Anbin, S. (2021). Recontextualizing constructive journalism in contemporary China: A comparative and intercultural perspective. *Social Sciences in China*, 42(2), 184–195. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02529203.2021.1924466>
- Cotos, E., Huffman, S., & Link, S. (2017). A move/step model for methods sections: Demonstrating rigour and credibility. *English for Specific Purposes*, 46(4), 90–106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2017.01.001>
- Deng, C. (2013). Comparative analysis of Chinese and English company profile genres. *Overseas English*, 11, 180–182 (in Chinese: 邓春梅. (2013) 中英文公司简介体裁对比分析. 海外英语, 11, 180 - 182.).
- Fairclough, N. (2003). *Analyzing Discourse*. Routledge.
- Fairclough, N. (2010). *Critical Discourse Analysis: The Critical Study of Language*. Routledge.
- Fetzer, A. (2017). Context. In H. Yan (Ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Pragmatics*. Oxford University Press.
- Hofstede, G. (2001). *Culture's Consequences: Comparing Values, Behaviors, Institutions, and Organizations Across Nations*. Sage Publications.
- Jie, L. (2012). Contrastive genre analysis of China-America pharmaceutical company profile. *Journal of Jiamusi Institute of Education* 9, 295-295 (in Chinese: 刘婕. (2012). 中美制药公司简介体裁对比分析. 佳木斯教育学院学报, (9), 295-295.).
- Li, J., & Zhu, W. (2020). Genre analysis of chairman's message in English annual reports of Chinese and foreign companies. *Overseas English*, 6, 91–94 (in Chinese: 李佳瑞, & 朱万忠. (2020). 中外公司英语年报中董事长致辞的体裁分析. 海外英语(6), 4.).
- Lin, W. (2021). An exploration of the English translation of the website of central enterprises under recontextualization: Taking CGNPC website as an example. *Overseas English*, 17, 200–201 (in Chinese: 王琳. (2021). 重新语境化下中央企业网站内容英译探析——以中广核集团网站为例. 海外英语(17), 2.).
- Linell, P. E. R. (1998). *Approaching Dialogue: Talk, Interaction and Contexts in Dialogical Perspectives*. John Benjamins.
- Swales, J. M. (2004). Research Genres: Exploration and applications. In *Cambridge University Press*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9781139524827.002>
- T.Hall, E. (1976). *Beyond Culture*. Doubleday.
- Tseng, M. (2018). Creating a theoretical framework: On the move structure of theoretical framework sections in research articles related to language and linguistics. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 33, 82–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2018.01.002>

- Wodak, R. (1999). Critical Discourse Analysis at the End of the 20th Century. *Research on Language & Social Interaction*, 32(1–2), 185–193. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08351813.1999.9683622>
- Wodak, R. (2001). *Methods of Critical Discourse Analysis* (R. W. M. Meyer (ed.); Vol. 148). Sage Publications.
- Wodak, R., & Fairclough, N. (2010). Recontextualizing European higher education policies: The cases of Austria and Romania. *Critical Discourse Studies*, 7(1), 19–40. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17405900903453922>
- Wu, J., & Dong, L. (2020). Re-contextualization and the foreign promotion of Chinese national culture. *Foreign Languages and Translation*, 3(2), 54–67. <https://doi.org/10.19502/j.cnki.2095-9648.2020.02.006> (in Chinese: 武建国, & 董丽雯. (2020). 重新语境化与中华国学文化的对外宣传——以孔子学院网页翻译为例. *外语与翻译*, 27(2), 6.)
- Wu, J., Huang, S., & Zheng, R. (2016). Recontextualization and transformation in media discourse: An analysis of the first-instance judgment of the Peng Yu Case. *Discourse and Society*, 27(4), 441–466. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0957926516634547>
- Wu, J., & Li, X. (2017). Recontextualization and the transmission of enterprise culture: A case study on the translation of the websites of Fortune Global 500. *Journal of Foreign Languages*, 40(2), 0–6 (in Chinese: 武建国, & 李昕蒙. (2017). 重新语境化与企业文化的传播——以世界五百强企业的网页翻译为例. *外国语*, 40(2), 7.)
- Huang, Y. (2004). Adhering to the three principles of closeness: Dealing with the difficult issues in external publicity. *Chinese Translators Journal*, 25(6), 27–28 (in Chinese: 黄友义. (2004). 坚持“外宣三贴近”原则, 处理好外宣翻译中的难点问题. *中国翻译*, 025(006), 27–28.)
- Zhang, S., & Zhao, Y. (2020). An analysis of the translation of the Fortune 500 Chinese company profiles from the perspective of recontextualization. *Journal of Hulunbuir University*, 72(2), 278–283 (in Chinese: 张世蓉, & 赵圆. (2020). 重新语境化下世界500强中国企业简介翻译探析. *呼伦贝尔学院学报*, 28(5), 5.)